

AI-DRIVEN DEEPPAKE TECHNOLOGY LITERACY: DETECTION METHODS, AND IMPACT ON CREDIBILITY & TRUST OF JOURNALISM

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15099836>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
05 February, 2025	05 March, 2025	20 March, 2025	28 March, 2025

ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven Deepfake technology is becoming increasingly prevalent today and poses a significant threat to journalists in terms of credibility and reliability of the media. Deepfakes, realistic images, videos, and audio generated with the use of Artificial Intelligence but are genuine fake, have become rampant. At first it was an entertainment tool and was noticed in the film industry, but after that deepfake started appearing in political circles: they use it to influence people and deceive them. This paper seeks to examine the awareness and understating of deep fakes in relation to media credibility, journalism principles and the sanctity of a news report. It explains how fake videos affect the society and looks into how one could tell whether the videos that they are using are real or fake. In addition, the study explores the possibilities of addressing the negative consequences of deepfakes, such as media literacy and the use of particular technologies. Finally, the paper outlines the strategies for journalism to embrace this new environment while endeavoring to stay truthful in the fake news world that is fast becoming a norm in the digital realm.

Keywords: Deepfake technology, AI, media trust, journalism credibility, disinformation, Artificial intelligence detection, media literacy, misinformation.

INTRODUCTION

The media industry in the last two decades has significantly developed through the advancement of the digital technologies that created new forms of content generation alongside the conventional ways of media production (Irfan and alQahtani, 2023). One of the many shake-ups that has occurred in this field is the use of deepfake technology. The term deepfakes refers to the AI and ML-generated images, videos, and audio contents

that are highly realistic yet completely fake (Chesney & Citron, 2019). This technology that was common in the entertainment sector and social media has turned out to bring mischief to political circles to spread fake news and control voters' emotions (Kietzmann & McCarthy, 2020; Irfan and Firdous, 2024; Irfan and Murray, 2023). Therefore, the threat of deep fakes poses a doom for journalists and any media

organization, and political authority that fights for the provision of credible information.

Background

Deepfake technology has been known since 2017 when the software that let swap faces in the video was released by merely using the technology called “face swap” (Maras & Alexandrou, 2019; Irfan, 2025). This was a pretty innocent form of deep fake but that gave the viewer a true idea of how much is possible with AI concerning visuals and so consequently gave a foretaste of the ethical crisis that is to come. In the course of evolution, deepfake has been brought to a higher level and is no longer just limited to manipulating faces; instead, deep fake produces entirely fake scenes and dialogs which are almost indistinguishable from the actual content (Fraga & Pontes, 2020). Thus, one of the most significant uses of realistic voice, facial expressions, and gestures has tied to the generation of sinful deep fakes for the purpose of delivering fake news, smearing, and manipulating the political elections (Zeng et al., 2020).

But the issue which deep fakes raise goes way beyond the technical level since it strikes at very fundamentals of professional journalism, mainly its mission to provide trustworthy information. Recent cases where deep fake videos of politicians or celebrities make some awful statements spread online have raised concerns with the increase in the ability to produce convincing content that might be a fake (Chesney & Citron, 2019). With increasing use of digital platforms for messages, those generated with the use of deepfakes harm the trust between the public and the news media organizations and potentially bring to doubt the future of truth in journalism.

Rationale of the Study

The reason for exploring deepfake technology and its impact on journalism is explained by the focusing of digital media in today’s society along with the further enhancement of artificial intelligence technology used in fake content creation. The effects of deepfakes are worse especially

given that the world today is experiencing an epidemic of fake news which makes it difficult to distinguish between reality and fake information. A considerable amount of people currently get their news through social networks, which do not have consistent levels of professional journalism standards (Maras & Alexandrou, 2019; Youcefi, Irfan and Aldylaylan, 2023). Consequently, it becomes increasingly easy for one to meet fake media which has not been equipped with ways of evaluating its veracity.

Further, deepfake erodes the trust of the audience in journalism to such an extent that it brings into question the fundamental aims of Postman – the media being the message. Journalism as a field has relied on some ethical values such as fairness, openness, and accuracy in practices that may be compromised by the fake content produced by AI in the current society. It is important to understand the threats that deep fakes present to these principles in order to consider how journalism might adapt to this altered environment.

Problem Statement

The problem of deepfake is becoming more and more acute now as it affects the credibility of the information in media and journalism. Since realist fake works alarmingly closely to the genuine articles, people face more and more challenges while trying to distinguish between real and fake news, inflating the bestowal of skepticism towards the information that circulates in society. It has been reported that deepfakes with the help of disinformation have already had political impact including election interference, slanderous attacks on public figures, and depennial of media outlets (Zeng et al., 2020; Khan, Azeem and Irfan, 2022; Khan et al., 2022). Despite the attempted development of such methods for detecting the fakes, the creation of deep fakes has advanced at a rate that outpaces current detection by both news organizations as well as fact-checking organizations and applications(Irfan et al., 2023; Irfan, Murray and Ali, 2023; Irfan, Murray and Ali, 2023) . This development becomes an important issue for journalism: how to meet these new

expectations while still holding journalism's core values of truth telling in a rapidly evolving digital world.

Research Objectives

- To analyse the impact of deepfake technology on the credibility of journalism and the media industry
- To evaluate the existing detection methods for deep fakes and identify their limitations.
- Investigate the role of digital literacy and media education in combating the spread of disinformation.
- To examine potential strategies for the media industry, including collaboration with technology companies and policymakers, to address the challenges posed by deepfakes.
- To provide recommendations for enhancing the ability of journalists to maintain the integrity of news and information in the face of emerging digital threats.

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of deepfake technology on trust in media?
2. To what extent are respondents confident in their ability to detect deepfake content?
3. What role do media literacy and education play in the effectiveness of deepfake detection tools?
4. How does deepfake technology affect the perceived credibility of journalism?

Literature Review

Deepfake technology is becoming increasingly popular and is a threat to the journalism and media industry. Since the advancement of state-of-the-art Algorithms, people have paid much attention on the AI's processing and generating capabilities for video, audio and text, thus raising the believability for the content derived from the internet. After that, the present literature review provides a theoretical framework of the given issue and empirical studies on the effects of deepfakes in journalism and media consumption, as well as in disseminating fake news.

Empirical Studies

There are several aspects that have been considered in empirical research regarding

deepfakes ranging from technical detection to the psychological and social impact of AI content. These works give useful information on the extent of the issue and potential working experience difficulties concerning deepfakes to journalists and media organizations.

One of the main research areas that have emerged in the modern world has been the development of methods for detection and identification of deepfakes. When it comes to more elaborate fake videos, the deception is even greater as Maras and Alexandrou (2019) pointed out, and identified what approaches digital forensic experts in identifying manipulated media. These studies have pointed out that perfective pixel forensic methods or any methods that check for artefacts due to lossy compression fail when used with deep fakes, because deepfakes are designed to disorient such methods by copying the natural textures and illumination of the true videos. Recent improvements consequently have been made regarding detecting notable changes in the context through the help of AI tools, though. Some of the algorithms that use facial movement tracking and deep neural networks to identify any irregularity in facial expressions or voice synthesis have been designed (Nguyen et al., 2019). However, the methods of identifying deepfakes in real-time remain a challenge because the technology is growing more advanced than the methods used to detect them.

Another research avenue is the psychological effect of deepfake on, or the effect it has on, media consumers. Zeng et al. (2020) notes that deep fake videos are more effective compared to other forms of fake news because it taps on the bandwidth of people in the sense that they trust more in what they hear and see. Analysing the results one can state that the viewers are able to trust the manipulated media if it looks like the real one even if they know that it is altered. This accords with what Lewandowsky et al. (2017) opined that people have preference towards content that supports their existing perceptions, making deepfakes an effective means of deploying fake news. Effects of deepfakes on the public and confidence in

the media are the following, the target audience may not distinguish real news from fake news.

Consequently, in light of media effects, various empirical studies have demonstrated that deepfakes can only make matters worse in a number of already existing problems of media manipulation. Kietzmann and McCarthy (2020) conducted a study wherein the authors sought to establish how deepfakes were employed within political contexts with emphasis to the 2016 United States of America's presidential election. Based on the results of the research, deepfake is not only a method of discrediting candidates but also misinformation as a means of influencing the voter's choice. This is in consonance with the study by Farkas and Neumayer (2017), regarding deepfakes as a category of political disinformation that may potentially cripple the electoral processes through widespread fake news on social media platforms. It further explained how deepfakes were complemented by social media since algorithms take the users to the content, regardless of reality.

Furthermore, legal and ethical analysis of the issue has revealed a discrepancy between the development of technology in creating deepfakes and the legal acts that regulate this process. Chesney and Citron (2019) have identified the need to enhance legislation to address deepfakes and mentioned that they are still faced with the following challenges: privacy, defamation, and free speech. There has been criticism about the laws currently in place to address deepfakes as they cannot keep up with the rate of production and distribution of the fake videos and audio; hence, the need for more cooperation on an international level and more strict measures to combat deepfakes.

Literature has also looked at the ethical questions posed in connection to how journalists handle deepfakes. Fraga and Pontes (2020) conducted a study and identified that journalists know that deepfakes are dangerous, but they are not certain how to prevent them from being spread, so they either partly or fully censor them. There are many existing ethical guidelines still not sufficiently defined

regarding the use of AI-generated content in journalism business and media organizations such as maintaining innovation while assuming the obligation to be factual and accurate.

There have been many research works on the non-supervisory solution of media literacy to mitigate the danger presented by deepfakes. Fraga & Pontes (2020) state that public awareness can be deemed as one of the most efficient means to combat deepfakes. In this regard, studies conducted by Lewandowsky et al. (2017), as well as Farkas and Neumayer (2017), show that the informed public can distinguish the actual fake news from the manipulated one. As the share of consumed digital media content grows, the inclusion of media literacy programs in teaching curricula has been suggested as a way to counteract the adverse effects of deepfakes.

Analyzing the existing literature regarding deepfake technology and its effects on journalism, one can conclude that the problem is far from being one-dimensional and straightforward. Nevertheless, some questions remain to be answered concerning the detection of deepfakes as well as logistics of their influence on the audience. Regarding the consumption of media, AI is a relatively new field into which additional research and advancement are needed in order to find appropriate solutions. This paper shows the very obvious understanding of the need to extend the current technological, ethical, and legal interventions to check on the deep fake news in as much as to enhance the credibility of journalism.

Methodology

This study used survey method as its source of collection for quantitative data from the target population (general-public), which includes news and media consumers. The survey method is most suitable for this study as it permits the researchers to obtain responses from a large pool of participants and therefore arrive at general conclusions regarding the link between deepfake technology, disinformation, media reliability, and journalism integrity.

The survey aimed to answer the key research questions that divided into sections based on

participants' awareness of deepfake technology, their ability to identify the detected content as a deepfake, their trust in digital media, and credibility of news organizations. The survey was based on multiple answer questions, Likert scales. The Likert scale applied as its questions help in assessing the attitude and perception of the respondents Demographic variables were also the part of the survey for which questions like age, gender, level of education and frequency of media usage will be asked.

Sampling Procedure

Regarding the sample selection, the study adopted the stratified random sample collection strategy to guarantee that the results can be generalized to a broader population. This approach enables a broader involvement of participants coming from different age, education and geographical

backgrounds. Data was collected from 500 respondents through online google form method.

Data Analysis

The collected data was using statistical tools e.i. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). To analyze the findings from the Likert scale questions, descriptive analysis such as frequencies, mean and standard deviation applied.

Results

The survey findings are significant concerning the basic understanding of deepfake technology, its influence on the trust in media and the role of journalism. The analysis was done under various headings and the results, in tables and figures mentioned above, is summarised as follows.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Survey Participants

Demographic Variable	Frequency (n = 500)	Percentage (%)
Age Group		
18-24 years	120	24%
25-34 years	150	30%
35-44 years	100	20%
45-54 years	80	16%
55+ years	50	10%
Education Level		
High School	80	16%
Undergraduate	200	40%
Graduate/Postgraduate	220	44%
Media Consumption		
Social Media (Daily)	320	64%
TV News (Daily)	150	30%
Print Media (Daily)	30	6%

6. Social Media Usage Frequency

The analysis of the survey results revealed that currently 64% of the respondents use social media daily, 24% use it in a week, 8% rarely use, while 4% have never used social media. The respondents further outline this in Table 2 showing the demographics relating to the frequent usage of social media. To

illustrate this kind of population distribution, a pie chart is used as shown in figure 6. The high level of daily usage shows that social media is a preferred source of news and information, which makes it even more important for social media platforms to improve the prevention of deepfake content.

Table 2: Media Consumption Habits of the respondents

Media Consumption Frequency	Frequency (n = 500)	Percentage (%)
Social Media Usage		
Daily	320	64%
Weekly	120	24%
Rarely	40	8%
Never	20	4%
TV News Consumption		
Daily	150	30%
Weekly	180	36%
Rarely	120	24%
Never	50	10%
Print Media Consumption		
Daily	30	6%
Weekly	60	12%
Rarely	150	30%
Never	260	52%

7. TV News Consumption Frequency

The frequency of accessing TV news reveals that 30% of respondents access it daily, 36% weekly, 24% rarely, and 10% do not access it at all. This data is as displayed in the Table 7 and graphically in Figure 1 in the form of a bar chart. The high percentage of respondents seen to be consuming TV news shows that people are still supplied with the

information through traditional media platforms. However, given the rising popularity of deep fakes and their credibility that diminishes the quality and reliability of the information through AI-generated video, audio or image forgeries, the TV news providers should develop stricter measures of checking the inputted content and collaborate more closely with social digital platforms.

Figure 1 TV News Consumption Frequency

Awareness of Deepfake Technology

The survey conducted among the sample showed that 75% of participants have heard of deepfake technology while 25% were ignorant of it. This is evident in the following table with the views of the respondents as indicated below in Table 3. The given results show that the majority of the respondents heard about deepfake technology which points to raising awareness of the public,

however a quarter of the respondents did not come across this term and thus, it is essential to Viet more attention to the problem. The outcome also matches the donut chart reported in figure 1 that encompasses the awareness between the participants who are aware and those who are not. These findings indicate a developing apprehension to deep fake technology as it continues to progress in its complexity.

Table 3: Awareness of Deepfake Technology

Awareness of Deepfake Technology	Frequency (n = 500)	Percentage (%)
Aware	375	75%
Not Aware	125	25%

2. Impact of Deepfakes on Media Trust

According to the survey, about 68% of the respondents felt that deepfakes have a negative influence on their trust in media, 20% of them do not feel the influence at all, and 12% of them feel that deepfakes have a positive influence. This is as depicted in table 3 showing the responses on perceived impact of deepfakes. The majority of the respondents reported that they felt that their trust in media had diminished due to

deepfakes, as seen in table 4. The frequency of people who disliked various media content due to deepfakes. It shows that the public needs to pay attention to technology that is likely to undermine the credibility of journalism. A feature analysis of the campaign also laid emphasis on the necessity where media houses should come up with proper strategies to curb disinformation.

Q1: What is the impact of deepfake technology on trust in media?

Table 4: Perceived Impact of Deepfake on Media Trust

Impact of Deepfakes on Media Trust	Frequency (n = 500)	Percentage (%)
Negative Impact	340	68%
No Impact	100	20%
Positive Impact	60	12%

3. Ability to Detect Deepfake Content

Additionally, 68% of participants stated that they did not feel certain in identifying deep fakes while only 32% reported that they were certain in doing so. This is evident as indicated in the table 5 below that shows the detection ability of the respondent. This clearly demonstrates that there are those that feel that they can easily identify deepfakes and those who rather cannot. Figure 3 is a stacked bar chart that emphasizes this to

indicate that the public has been outsmarted by deep fake technology through highlighting this element hence it is hard to detect. These indicate the need for better methods of detecting fake media and adequate sensitization on existing fake media detection techniques.

Q2: To what extent are respondents confident in their ability to detect deepfake content?

Table 5: Ability to Detect Deepfake Content

Ability to Detect Deepfake Content	Frequency (n = 500)	Percentage (%)
Confident in Detection	160	32%
Not Confident in Detection	340	68%

Q3: What role do media literacy and education play in the effectiveness of deepfake detection tools?

4. Effectiveness of Media Literacy and Detection Tools

Regarding, the respondents suggest the effectiveness of media literacy programs and detection technologies. A majority (55%) said that media literacy can help deal with deepfakes, while only 40% said that

technology alone is enough to detect them. A fifth of the participants believed that both media literacy programs and detection tools were effective in some way. The figure 2 shows the public perspective on the same. However, as it has been described in this paper, there remains a critical need for advanced technological solutions for detecting deepfakes as media literacy is viewed as a more effective measure.

Figure 2 Effectiveness of Media Literacy and Detection Tools

8. Responses Regarding Deepfake Detection Education

In the case of education on deep fake detection, table 6 indicates that 74% of the participants had little or no knowledge on how to detect deep fakes and only 16% used online guides and 10% had undergone formal training. This war narrows the gap of knowledge on deepfake detection down to a

very thin line. The picture of education in deepfake as it has been represented through the figures is this one presented in table 8 in word cloud format regarding the responses about deepfake detection. This suggests that there is a need for incorporation of deepfake detection in the media literacy programmes and ensuring the public has what it takes to effectively distinguish fake items from real content.

Table 6: Responses Regarding Deepfake Detection Education

Type of Education/Training for Deepfake Detection	Frequency (n = 500)	Percentage (%)
Received Formal Training	50	10%
Received Informal Education (e.g., online guides)	80	16%
No Education	370	74%

Q4: How does deepfake technology effect the perceived credibility of Journalism?

5. Trust in Journalism's Credibility

Regarding the level of trust in journalism, 74% of the respondents had no trust in journalism; 20% had some level of trust in journalism; and 6% had full level of trust in journalism. The following is depicted in the table below where the respondents have given their level of trust in journalism in the

age of deep fakes as indicated in Table 6. Figure 5 is a 3D bar chart that depicts the clear difference as well. Based on the results of the survey, it can be stated that deepfake impairs the legitimacy of journalism to a significantly large extent. Journalism cannot be trusted to function this way; therefore, it is on the obligation to alter to these new challenges by ensuring the veracity of news that is taken to the public.

Table 7: Trust in Journalism's Credibility in the Age of Deepfakes

Trust in Journalism's Credibility	Frequency (n = 500)	Percentage (%)
No Trust	370	74%
Some Trust	100	20%
Full Trust	30	6%

The survey results reveal that there is a lack of familiarity with deepfake technology, its benefits, as well as the capacity to address the concerns that it raises. This mixed finding shows that while more people are familiar with deepfakes, none of them are confident in their ability to identify such fake media, and there is equally low confidence in journalism information content. Despite the positive reception of media literacy programs, there is a push for more technological advancements and the need for learning how to identify deepfakes. It recommended that the media organizations and the digital platform cooperate in order to help verify content that is circulating around and also the public should be taught on how to differentiate between a fake news and a deep fake one in order to regain trust in journalism and all things related to media.

Discussion

Deepfake technology is very dangerous for journalism, people's trust, and media as a whole. The current study sought to establish the effects of deepfakes, the general public's capacity to identify fakes and the efficacy of demands such as media literacy initiatives and technologies in addressing this issue. The results of the survey indicate therefore that even though awareness of deepfakes has grown, there are many areas of knowledge deficiency and lack of available tools to address the threats posed by the use of this technology. This discussion situates the survey within the overall conversation and draws correlations with existing research on deepfakes and media trust.

Impact of Deepfakes on Public Trust and Journalism

About 64% of participants reported a drop in their trust levels in media and news since

the emergence of deepfake pornography, and 92% said that deepfake videos have the potential to bring significant harm in their society. The majority of the respondents claimed to have found it difficult to trust the journalism due to deepfakes this side was supported by a similar study done by Lazer et al. (2018) revealing that manipulated media dilute the public's confidence in news sources. Deepfakes are based upon the fact that people believe visual and auditory signals, which are considered to be authentic information ones. While deepfakes were once obvious and easily recognizable, the public may nowadays mistake them for genuine stories since even highly reputable media outlets have no shield against such fake content.

To be specific, recent studies state that people tend to receive information presented in the media with more suspicion today because of deepfakes and other forms of digital manipulation (Franks, 2020). Their significant experience is worrisome to journalism since the credibility of the media in its work is paramount. When trust is lacking, therefore, journalism ceases to play the role of educating the public as well as shaping opinion. According to the findings of this study, in relation to mitigating challenges posed by deepfakes, media firms require special intervention measures to try to regain public trust, including work with technology companies to advance the state of the art in detecting fake content and to improve how the news industry reports on the processes used to check the credibility of content (Binns, 2020).

Detection Challenges and Public Awareness

According to this study, more than half of the survey participants said they were not sure about how to distinguish deepfakes.

That is why one of the points that scholars have noted is the lack of awareness of manipulated media among the public (Chesney & Citron, 2019). There are existing detection tools for detection of deepfake videos such as AI software that is capable of detecting visual and audible deviations in fake videos, often in terms of visuals as well as audio although they are not common in use and most often they may not be easily understandable by everybody (Kietzmann & McCarthy, 2020). Moreover, as the FOFs for creating deepfakes progress, there is a need to detect them and the means to do so, which is likewise advancing as well. This is so because digital literacy programs have not effectively captured many of the issues involved in modern media manipulation (Franks, 2020). There is one field which can contribute to the overall increase in people's ability to detect deepfakes and it is education in terms of digital literacy. Research carried out in the past has revealed that media literacy is one of the most powerful tools that would help to fight fake news and other related digital media manipulation (Lewandowsky et al., 2017). These findings are corroborated by the findings of this survey where the respondents said that media literacy could go a long way in combating deepfakes. This resonates with other scholars and policy makers who advocate for digital literacy as part of school education, so that people will have the necessary skills to enable them to deal with the complexities of the developing media (McGrew et al., 2018; Irfan, Aldulaylan and Alqahtani, 2023). Still, according to the responses gathered, there is a lot of effort that has to be made to raise awareness of the public about the existence of deepfake technology and available methods for the detection of such fakes.

Effectiveness of Current Interventions

As a result of the survey, it was observed that media literacy programs were considered to be more effective than the detection technologies. Although this seems to show that there is acknowledgment of the importance of education when it comes to addressing deepfakes, it also points out that technology-based remedies are lacking.

However, at present, deepfake technologies are still not advanced enough for widespread and real-time use. Due to this, there is a worry that technology has not been able to advance at the same pace as the increasingly sophisticated methods of creating deepfakes (Kietzmann & McCarthy, 2020). Thus, according to the presented survey findings, the participants believe that the current detection technologies are inadequate, implying that the improvement and accessibility of these tools are needed to counter the threat of deepfakes.

Similarly, it is also revealed that though media literacy is perceived as an effective measure, one can doubt its effectiveness in resolving the issue connected with deepfakes in full. Media literacy, as well as the detection of the fake media, must, therefore, go hand in hand to help in the fight against deepfake (Franks, 2020). Awareness schemes of the public can effectively prevent such iterations but without the technical means of evaluating the information presented through media one can easily get duped. The news consumers who want to counter fake news should have capacity for technological support for verification of the content (McGrew et al., 2018).

Social Media's Role in the Spread of Deepfakes

Another important discovery stated by the survey is that social networking sites are some of the most common sources of news where 64% of the respondents regularly access their news through social media sites daily. In view of the fact that deepfakes are mostly spread through social media, this figure is quite alarming. It has also been established that fake news dissemination is more efficient in social media as compared to other over-the-top news sources because of the viral nature of the social media platforms (Vosoughi et al., 2018). Another important aspect and one of the reasons disinformation is hard to stop is the fast sharing of deepfakes on social media platforms. During the past several years, social media sites, which are optimized for user interactions, contribute to sharing stunning fake images and texts at the expense of their credibility, hence extending the

spread of deepfakes and misinformation (Pennycook & Rand, 2018).

Another of the issues brought up in the literature is the use of social media in enhancing the impact of deep fakes (Franks, 2020). Some companies such as Facebook and Twitter have in recent times introduced fact-checking measures, but the success of these measures is still questionable. Studies have also shown that new laws and improved technologies like the intelligent deep fake detection and the use of the block chain applications are needed to contain the spread of deep fakes on the social media (Pennycook & Rand, 2018). These result are in tandem with such calls for enhanced social media regulation to mitigate on the effects that arise from deep fake technology.

Conclusion

It is concluded that there is an urgent need for solution to address the consequences of the deepfake technology and the trust people have in the media, as well as journalism as a profession. The outcome of the study explored that although people are familiar with deepfakes, knowledge of identifying fake media is still direly inadequate. In addition, the common people do not trust journalism anymore as much as they because of the deepfakes. This means that the solutions should embrace the integration of media literacy education as well as enhancing improved detection technology that can easily incorporated in the regular use of media by the public. The media industry has to work together with the academia in trying to regain public confidence that make the journalism an effective and accurate method of passing information in the glob.

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